

**INTRINSIC MOTIVATION CORRELATION
AND SOCIAL SUPPORT WITH SELF-EFFICACY OF YOUTH
ON LEMBAGA PEMASYARAKATAN KHUSUS ANAK (LPKA)
TANGERANG, INDONESIA**

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Abstract:

Main purpose of this research is to see the correlation of intrinsic motivation and social support with self-efficacy of Youth on Lembaga Pemasyarakatan Khusus Anak (LPKA) Tangerang. (Ha1): there is correlation between intrinsic motivation with self-efficacy. (Ha2): there is correlation between social support with self-efficacy. (Ha3): there is correlation between intrinsic motivation and social support with self-efficacy. The research population is Youth on LPKA Tangerang with total of 82 peoples. Researcher's sampling using saturation sampling techniques (census) based on Likert scale. Measurement of intrinsic motivation scale consist of 34 valid items, with coefficient correlations range between 0.512 until 0.693 with 0.885 reliability. Efficacy scale consist of 23 valid items with correlations range between 0.631 until 0.738 with 0.736 reliability. From the result of bivariate correlation analysis known that $r = 0.241$, means (Ho1) rejected and (Ha1) accepted. Result test of (Ha2) known that $r = 0.244$, means (Ho2) rejected and (Ha2) accepted. From the test result of multivariate correlation known that $R = 0.298$, means (Ho3) rejected and (Ha3) accepted. Based on the result of this research, there is positive correlation between intrinsic motivation and social support with self-efficacy of Youth on LPKA Tangerang. The better of intrinsic motivation and the higher social support received by Subject, the higher self-efficacy of the Subject.

Keywords: self-efficacy, intrinsic motivation, social support

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1. Introduction

Indonesia is a state-law, as contained in Article 1 Paragraph 3 of the 1945 Constitution. Means every Indonesian citizen should be based on applicable law in behavior and actions. Anyone who violates the law, will be penalized. Part of the Indonesian citizens are teenager, those who need a social support to motivate themselves to grow to become a good people and to increase their self-confidence good to themselves and everyone around them. Adolescence is a transition process from childhood to become adult, this is a critical moment that determines how children will be growth and developed. According to Remplein (Niken Widanarti and Aisah Indati; 2002 : 114) critical moment is a period of crisis time with symptoms that shows the existence of distortion in growth and development. Growth and development to each child are different. Depends on the environment that the child grows and develops. Many teenagers whose development led into negative actions, and caught in trouble against the law, so-called Youths.

Lembaga Pemasyarakatan Khusus Anak (LPKA) in Tangerang is a government institution under the auspices of Ministry of Law and Human Rights in Banten. They use a guidance system for children who act against the law. Such children who are fostered and assisted so they can solve their problems and legally free from any charges. During their detention, the children were sent to school inside LPKA and taught special skills so once they set free, they have skills to continue their life normally. This certainty can happen if the subject has a good self-efficacy. Thus, he/she put some effort within themselves to achieve their tasks.

Self-efficacy is an individual ability and belief to carry out a task to achieve particular goal, Bandura (in Baron and Byrne, 2003 : 183). Self-efficacy has an important role to determine the actions to be taken and has a major effect on a person's behavior. In self-efficacy, there is an attempt to achieve the tasks, and one that distinguished from one individual to another is within him / herself effort. To achieve a goal, individuals must have an intrinsic motivation. With intrinsic motivation, man can be enthusiastic that will affect driving force to produce something better for themselves and their environment. According to Aditya and Agus Frianto (2013 : 378), intrinsic motivation could be arisen within the individual without any coercion or encouragement from the others, but based on their own will. Motivation could keep growing and thrive within individual if the environment encourages individuals to achieve particular tasks, therefore, that can be said that individual cannot live alone. In each individual's life, he / she needs each other. From this basic need we recognize, individual really need the support from the surrounding environment, it is called social support. Social support is a support to foster self-efficacy and intrinsic motivation within individuals.

According to Papalia, Olds, Feldman (2009 : 12), Social Support could help people to relieve the negative potential impact both physically and mentally. Youth who are serving their criminal sentences in LPKA Tangerang have different self-efficacy from one to another. This appears in Youth motivation when they run their activities inside LPKA

Tangerang. The social support they receive also varies. Moreover, there are some Youth who considered as missing people simply because their family never visit them.

Based on the background's problems stated above, following are formulation of problems:

- 1) is there any correlation between intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy on Youth at LPKA Tangerang?
- 2) is there any correlation between social support and self-efficacy on Youth at LPKA Tangerang?
- 3) is there any correlation between intrinsic motivation and social support with self-efficacy on Youth at LPKA Tangerang?

The purposes of this research are as follows:

- 1) to know the correlation between intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy on Youth at LPKA Tangerang.
- 2) to know the correlation between social support and self-efficacy on Youth at LPKA Tangerang.
- 3) to know the correlation between intrinsic motivation and social support with self-efficacy on Youth at LPKA Tangerang.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Self-Efficacy

Bandura (in Baron and Byrne, 2003 : 183) self-efficacy is Self-efficacy is an individual ability and belief to carry out a task to achieve particular goal.

Alwisol (in Nobelina Adicondro and Alfi Purnamasari, 2011 : 20) stated that self-efficacy could be obtained, modified, enhanced or reduced, through one or the combination of four sources, i.e. performance accomplishment, vicarious experiences, social persuasion and emotional / psychological states.

Bandura (in Nobelina Adicondro and Alfi Purnamasari, 2011 : 19) stated that self-efficacy has a major influence towards behavior. It can be amplified by the opinion of M. Nur Ghufon and Rini Risnawati (2010 : 75) that stated that the individual who has high self-efficacy believe that the he / she is able to perform his / her tasks, whereas, the individual who has low self-efficacy basically consider his / herself unable to perform his / her tasks.

From all the definitions of self-efficacy stated above, we come to the conclusion that self-efficacy is individual beliefs towards self ability to accomplish one's tasks.

According to Bandura (1997 : 42) self-efficacy has 3 aspects:

a. The Level

The difference in self-efficacy lived by each individual may be caused by different causes. Task demands are a representation of various difficulties in achieving optimal performance. If the difficulty to achieve these goals is just a little then, the activity is easier to do and then the individual will have high self-efficacy.

b. The Generality

Generality refers to the degree to which self-efficacy beliefs are positively related, either within a behavioral domain, across behavioral domains or across time. Generality is evaluated by measuring self-efficacy beliefs over the dimensions of concern. Generality of self-efficacy expectancies refers to the extent to which success or failure experiences influence self-efficacy expectancies in a limited, behaviorally specific manner, or whatever changes in self-efficacy expectancies extend to other similar behaviors and contexts (behavior, cognitive and affective).

c. The Strength

Experience had affect towards self-efficacy which is believed by the individuals. Weak experience will reduce their believe. Strength of self-efficacy has been related repeatedly to persistence in the face of frustration, pain, and other barriers to performance.

2.2 Intrinsic Motivation

Aditya and Agus Frianto (2013 : 378) consider that intrinsic motivation could be arisen within the individual without any coercion or encouragement from the others, but based on their own will. Hamzah B. Uno (2014 : 66) amplified in his statement, that intrinsic motivation may arise and requires no external stimulation since it exists in each individuals, in line with the needs.

Juliani (2007 : 10) has an opinion that intrinsic motivation is a driving force or impulse that exists in human which arises, directs and organizes behavior. Meanwhile, according to Hamzah B. Uno (2014 : 7) intrinsic motivation Intrinsic motivation becomes the identification of the behavior of someone who feels happy about something. If the individual likes the activity, then the individual will be motivated to do it.

M. Nur Ghufron & Rini Risnawati (2010 : 87) stated that intrinsic motivation is a form of motivation that comes from within an individual in addressing a task and job that can provide inner satisfaction for the individual.

Schunk and Pintrich (2012 : 359) stated that intrinsic motivation tend to be contextual. Intrinsic motivation may change over time. Whereas, Aditya and Agus Frianto (2013 : 377) stated that intrinsic motivation involves individuals who carry out an activity because of interest so as to obtain immediate satisfaction from the activity itself.

White (Schunk and Pintrich, 2012 : 361) states that intrinsic motivation is global and focused on environmental features that capture their attention. Furthermore Ryan (in M. Nur Ghufron & Rini Risnawita, 2010: 86) added that the environment can make a person's intrinsic motivation weaken and also strengthen. He also stated that the environment could make an individual intrinsic motivation weaken or strengthen.

From all the definitions of intrinsic motivation stated above, we come to the conclusion that intrinsic motivation is could be arises from the individual itself without any coercion or encouragement of others and could be weaken or strengthen because of the environment.

Schunk and Pintrich (2012 : 363) state that intrinsic motivation has five aspects:

- a. Preference towards challenge, rather than easy tasks. From the explanation, an example could be taken such as work hard on a challenging tasks and like to solve difficult problems.
- b. The working incentives are self-interest and curiosity satisfaction rather than working to please the teacher and getting a good grade. For example, always ask regarding new things and eager to solve the problem.
- c. Self-mastery, rather than depends on the teachers. For example, having a confidence of their own result and be able to overcome the problems.
- d. Independent assessment, rather than rely on the teacher's assessment. Example, cling on to their own opinion and working on to their own desires.
- e. Internal criteria, rather than external ones, related to success and failure. Example, having an awareness regarding their own capabilities and responsible for the achieved result.

2.3 Social Support

Baron and Byrne (in Nobelina Adicondro and Alfi Purnamasari, 2011 : 20) stated social support is a physical and psychological comfort provided by friends or family members. Amplified by the opinions of Papalia, Olds and Feldman (2009 : 12) that social support could help individual's negate the potential negative effect of stress on physical and mental health. Social support can be done by family members, colleagues, community, a professional person even a volunteer (Lubis, N.L. and Othman, M.H.B., 2011 : 66).

Meanwhile, Sarafino (in Johana, Aries and Ervy, 2007 : 83) stated social support refers to comfortability, care, self-esteem or any form of aid that received by individuals from others or groups. This could mean comfort and care, in any form that is given by the closest peoples could be valuable support for the individuals.

Miftahun Ni'mah and Sugiyanto (2010 : 97) stated social support is a form of interpersonal relationships with individuals that near, which include a provision of assistance such as empathy that could be given in communication process, social contact which giving a pleasure, helping awards from others, also feel cared for the individuals that received helps or supports.

In line with the opinion of Sri Maslihah (2011 : 106) stated everything contained in the environment could be a social support or not, depends on the individuals feels as a social support.

From the definitions above, concluded that social support is a sense of acceptance that obtained from togetherness and social intimacy that arise from comfortability both physically and mentally that can reduce the potential impact of stress.

Sarafino (in Johana, Aries and Ervy, 2007 : 82 – 83) stated basicly there are five types of social support:

a. Emotional Support

This kind of support includes empathy, care and individual concern. Usually, this kind of supportive actions obtained from spouse or family, for example giving an

understanding of problems or listening to a complaint. This kind of support will provide sense of comfort, assurance and love.

b. Award Support

This kind of support occurs through positive appreciation for individuals, encouragement to go forward or approval of ideas and positive individual comparison with others. Usually, this kind of support actions obtained from superior and colleagues. This kind of support will provide valuable and competent feels.

c. Instrumental Support

This kind of support includes direct assistance. Usually this kind of support actions obtained from friends or colleagues. For example, assistance to complete some tasks that had been accumulated or money-lending or other necessary.

d. Informative Support

This kind of support includes provision of advice, suggestions or feedback. This kind of support actions obtained from friends, colleagues, superiors or professional such as doctors or psychologists.

e. Network Support

By giving the feeling that the individual is a member of some group and had the same interests. Sense of togetherness with group members is a support for the individual. Based on the theories above, following hypothesis will be proposed: (H1) there is a relationship between intrinsic motivation with self-efficacy in Youth at LPKA Tangerang. (H2) there is a relationship between social support and self-efficacy in Youth at LPKA Tangerang. (H3) there is relationship between intrinsic motivation and social support with self-efficacy in Youth at LPKA Tangerang.

3. Research Method

Self-efficacy is an individual belief to perform some actions, tasks, by using whole ability that individuals had. This research purposes is to measure self-efficacy of the Youth through self-efficacy scale that includes Level, Generality and Strength.

Intrinsic motivation is a drive or desire of the individuals that has a valuable meanings for and individuals to perform their daily activities. In this research, to measure intrinsic motivation by using an intrinsic motivation scale through preference of challenge, work incentives are satisfied self-interest and curiosity, self-mastery, independent assessment and internal criteria.

Social support is a sense of acceptance that obtain from togetherness and social intimacy that rises from comfortability both physically and mentally that can reduce the potential impact of stress. In this research, social support for Youth is measured through social support scales includes emotional support, award support, instrumental support, informative support and network support. Data collection of this research by using Likert's scale method. The scale method is a data collection method that contains a number of written questions and statement to the subject with intention to obtain information about the investigated problems.

In this research, by using a method of saturation sampling (Census), where all members of populations are using as a samples. This methods usage based on the small population number, which is only 82 peoples.

In this research, the validity of items (with significance level of 5%) and statistical method for analyzing the data were calculated by using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Then using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient Formula to find the reliability. The calculation done by using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) for windows version 15.

4. Research and Data Analysis

From the result of research data analysis, by using bivariate techniques between intrinsic motivation and self-efficacy variables obtained correlation coefficient values of $r = 0.241$, it shows "there is a relationship between intrinsic motivation with self-efficacy in Youth at LPKA Tangerang" positively, means the higher intrinsic motivation is, the higher self-efficacy.

Based on the second hypothesis, by using bivariate techniques (correlation between variables) between social support and self-efficacy obtained correlation coefficient values of $r = 0.244$, it shows "there is a relationship between social support and self-efficacy in Youth at LPKA Tangerang" positively, means the higher social support received, the higher self-efficacy is.

The R (double correlation coefficient) score was obtained with amount 0.298 with R square = 0.089. the score shows that both variables contribution to self-efficacy by 8.9% ($0.089 \times 100\%$). By detailed, social support effective contribution to self-efficacy around 6% ($0.060 \times 100\%$), meanwhile intrinsic motivation effective contribution to self-efficacy around 2.9% ($8.9\% - 6\%$). It shows the social support variable is stronger variable that influence self-efficacy more than intrinsic motivation. It means "there is relationship between intrinsic motivation and social support with self-efficacy in Youth at LPKA Tangerang". The higher intrinsic motivation in the individuals and social support that has been received, the higher the perceived self-efficacy.

After that, the normality test is carry out. It aims to see whether the data of research were normally distributed or not. The normality test in this research using the Shapiro Wilk's, as test respondents less than 100 peoples. Based on the normality test, the significance level of intrinsic motivation is 0.377, means that $p > 0.05$ so the intrinsic motivation data is normally distributed. Meanwhile the significance level of social support is 0.830, means that $p > 0.05$ so the social support data is normally distributed too. The significance level of self-efficacy is 0.172, means that $p > 0.05$ so the self-efficacy data is normally distributed.

From the categorization result, the mean of the intrinsic motivation is 120.2073 that placed it in the middle category and the mean of the social support is 105.3171 which means it is in the middle category too, and the mean of self-efficacy is 75.8171, means that placed in the middle category.

5. Conclusion

Therefore, based on the research it can be concluded that a good intrinsic motivation within individuals and matched with existence of social support has a relationship with self-efficacy of Youth in LPKA Tangerang. Intrinsic motivation and social support within the subjects are in the middle category and the self-efficacy, as it seen, in the middle category too. It shows that in addition to the intrinsic motivation and social support, there are another factors involved to the subject self-efficacy, due to the intrinsic motivation and social support only contributed by 8.9%.

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